

CAUSES OF THE YELWA SHENDAM PLATEAU STATE CRISIS IN 2002 AND 2004

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Abstract

This study investigates the underlying causes of the 2002 and 2004 Yelwa-Shendam crisis of 2002 and 2004, a violent conflict between ethnic groups in Plateau State, Nigeria. The research identifies key factors contributing to the crisis, including and religious tensions, competition for land and resources, political manipulation and elite interests, historical grievances, and unresolved conflicts. The study primarily adopted the historical methodology, employing the use of primary and secondary sources, such as oral interviews, published literature, journals, and articles for data collection and reconstruction of history, through a qualitative analysis of historical records, this study examines the complex interplay of these causes, highlighting the role of contextual and structural drivers. The findings provide insights into the dynamics of the crisis and inform strategies for conflict prevention and resolution in the plateau state of Yelwa Shendam and Nigeria at large.

1.1 Introduction

Violent conflict, commonly known as crisis, varies in scale and intensity. Over the years, it has been observed in different parts of the world. The exact number of these crises is difficult to ascertain, but it is safe to say that these social unrests have taken a toll on humanity in terms of deaths, displacement, and disruption of economic activities in markets and other commercial centers²

Conflict refers to the use of force and armed violence in pursuit of incompatible interests and goals. In recent years, violent conflict has erupted between ethnic groups in the former Yugoslavia, Russia, England, the United States, and Spain³. Conflict is also a threat to world peace and security, which always brings profound effects

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²Otite. O, Alberto. Community Conflict in Nigeria: *Management, Resolution, and Transformation* (Ibadan spectrum books 1999) Pp.45

³M. Zweiri, M. Zahid, Religion, ethnicity and identity politics in the Persian Gulf. Research institute for European and American Research Paper No. 111 (July 2007). p. 25

on warring communities and the nation-state. Forcibly displacing and destroying lives and properties, economies are always brought to a standstill.

As a continent, Africa has witnessed and experienced its share of these violent conflicts, ranging from the pre-colonial, colonial, and post-colonial eras. During the twentieth century, armed conflicts in Africa caused an enormous loss of life, the collapse of socio-economic activities, and the degradation of health and educational services across the continent. From the 1999 Somali civil war, the 1967–1970 Nigerian civil war of 1967-1970, Congo civil war of 1960 and the Rwanda genocide.⁴ These 20th century conflict submitted civilians to intense physical and psychological trauma that negatively impacted the development of many African nations.

Nigeria has recorded bitter experiences of violent conflict in various forms. Since the late 1960s, violent conflicts, commonly known as crises, have become re-occurring decimal Among the 36 states that constitute Nigeria, virtually none has not witnessed one form of conflict or the other.⁵ The spate of violence has been on a steady increase since Nigeria's independence, which has significantly disrupted the state's functionality, with the Ijaw and Itsekiri crisis in Warri over the Olu of Warri kingship, the Aguleri and Umuleri violent conflict in Anambra in 1999, the Tarok and Bogghom crisis in Wase, Plateau 2001, and the Sharia conflict in Kaduna.⁶ These examples illustrate the persistent and widespread nature of violent conflict across Nigeria, many of which remain intractable.

While violent conflict in plateau state shares similarities with other regional conflicts, it stands out due to its use of indigene status as a criterion for political, economic, and resource allocation. Religious differences have often acted as catalysts, intensifying the violence between indigenes and settlers competing for resources.⁷ In Jos, the state capital, insecurity has reached alarming levels, marked by frequent ethnic and communal clashes and other social vices, leading to an annual episode of violent conflict and bloodshed.⁸

Yelwa is a cosmopolitan area with a large Hausa/Fulani population, as there are also inhabitants from other tribes in the Shendam Local Government area. The Yelwa central market, which is the largest commercial center in Shendam, has experienced a devastating crisis that engulfed the local government in 2003 and 2004.

Shendam is a local government in plateau state, located in the southern part of plateau state. It is boarded by Quaanpan Local Government to the west, Langtang North to the east, Ibi Local Government of Taraba State to the south, Pankshin Local Government to the north, and Mikang Local Government to the south east⁹. The head quarter of the local government is also situated in Shendam.

Shendam is found on the Jos Plateau lowland and is characterized by undulating fertile grassland with mountain range only to the northern and north-west of the area. The study area is located at latitude 9^o N and longitude 9.5^o E¹⁰ and is situated south of the plateau hills in the Pankshin vicinity. However, it is separated from them only by a relatively narrow strip of the country.

The Yelwa central market, an economic hub, is located west of Shendam. It is situated at a longitude of 4.7^o E and latitude 10.9^o N.¹¹ The total distance between Yelwa and Shendam is 562 km and 250.41 m.¹² the area in

⁴Source: <https://Online.norwich.edu/online/about/resource-library/largest-naval-sea-battles-military-histor>. Accessed November 2, 2024...

⁵Osaghae, E. E. (1998). *The Crippled Giant: Nigeria since independence*. Indiana University press (1998), Pp.49

⁶Udefi, A. (2014). The Nigerian Experience of Democracy and the Burden of Ethno-Sectarian Conflicts. *The Journal of Pan African studies* (2014) .6 (10). Pp. 69-71.

⁷Mamman E.Bulus, *Public policy response to violence: case study of book haram insurgency in Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University 2020) retrieved 4 November 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.www.2020.010>

⁸Krause, J. (2010). A Deadly Cycle: *Ethno-Religious Conflict in Jos Plateau State*, Nigeria Working Paper, Geneva: Switzerland 2010 retrieved online 4 November 2024

⁹Sen Luka Gwom, "This is Shendam" (Nigeria: Fab Anieh Ltd, 1991), 4.

¹⁰Ames C.G. Gazetteer of the Northern Province of Nigeria. "The Highland Chieftaincies Plateau Province" (Vol.4No.127:London 1934)p.183

¹¹L.D. Walu, "Short History of Nshar Market in a Program for Bit Goemai Annual Festival" (RAXGS Publishers).1998), p. 7.

¹²Interview with MrElvis Didi, a geography graduate, 40 years old, at Longvel 20 December 2024.

question is located in Nigeria's Guinea Savannah region. At its core, the yelwa shendam conflict is accompanied by the destruction of properties, loss of life, and stagnation of economic activities. Therefore, the current study critically examines the devastating effects of the Yelwa Shendam violent conflict on the development of the Yelwa central market from 2003 to 2015.

1.2 The theoretical framework

To demystify the complexities of historical research, as in other disciplines, theories are employed to provide a concrete basis for argument, discussing ideas, and perspectives. These are ideas or beliefs or views arrived at by facts or principles. A theory should be able to explain the attitudes and characteristics under social investigation and be capable of projecting facts. However, there are numerous theories that explain conflict; each is an attempt by a scholar or group of scholars to analyze the historical, social, economic, philosophical, and even biological realities using concrete facts, prepositions, and principles that explain the causes, dynamics, and impacts of conflict of all kinds in and between societies.¹³

There are several theories of conflict and its impacts on commercial centers; however, the research will adopt the power and economic theories of conflict.

Power theory

The "Power Theory" is postulated by Morgenthau Hans, Clausewitz, and Nebuer. The proponents of this theory posit that states and nations operate in their own interests and that politics is a struggle for power and supremacy.¹⁴ The theory provides a pragmatic view of how actors react violently. This is viewed a selfish pursuit of interest. There are two stages of the power view of conflict in human society.¹⁵ The first level is the comprehension of the international system as chaotic and according to the proponents of this theory:

*Terrain of incompatible interests creates room for discord and conflict. This is seen due toas the result of one or more actors' insatiable quest for self-fulfillment of national interest, which also goes contrary to other actors.*¹⁶

The second perspective and the starting point of power theory is the analysis of conflict in the individual understanding of human nature. This view conceives individual interest as the prime mover of conflict because there is "an apparent weakness and individualism inherent in human nature that tends to make an individual self-centered, avaricious, and thus, naturally inclined to conflicts."¹⁷ Therefore, power politics theory argued that the inevitability of competition and conflict makes it an inevitable natural process for actors to prepare to deal with the outcome and consequences of conflicts. However, the emphasis placed by the theory on power as a means to an end overlooks state actors, who have a significant role in shaping the international system.¹⁸

In view of the above preposition, the conflict in Shendam local government, which started in 2003 and 2004, has been attributed to the struggle for power and economic control among various nationalities.

The -Economic Theory of Conflict

Another important theory considered in this research is the "Economic Theory of conflict". The theory examines the causes of conflicts and analyzes the interests of the perpetrators of conflicts in terms of resource control. Fundamental questions, such as who gains and who loses, have been asked by this theoretical perspective. The theory assumes that resource control, material benefit, or interest is the motivating factor and the most important issue at stake in conflict situations". In his analysis of conflict, Collier posits the following:

¹³Coser, L. A. (1975). "Social Conflict and the Theory of Social Change." *The British Journal of Sociology*, 8 (1975): 197-207.

¹⁴Ademola, F.S. (2006). *Theories of social conflicts*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books Ltd. 2006)

¹⁵Ibid

¹⁶Ademola, F.S. (2006). *Theories of social conflicts*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books Ltd. 2006)

¹⁷Ibid

¹⁸Ibid.

Conflicts are perpetrated by those who benefit from chaos, also referred to as “conflict entrepreneurs, who not only steer conflict but also invest resources at their disposal to ensure that conflict lingers on maximization of material benefit”¹⁹.

The economic theory of conflict also posits that the causes of conflict may be hidden and exacerbated in disguise of ideological (nationalism or political freedom) or even religious differences, where the aforementioned motive is mainly a contest for control over economic resources, assets, and control of commercial centers. Furthermore, the proponents of this theory emphasized the exploitative relationship between actors, which leads to conflicts with material interests, as the central factor that generates conflict.²⁰

In this context, Blagojevic asserts that

Political entrepreneurs mobilize ethnic constituencies by promoting inter-ethnic animosities using the rhetorical weapons of blame, fear, and hate to create in-group/out-group categories to achieve their objectives.²¹

However, the economic theory of conflict also explains the struggle for the control of economic resources and commercial centers, such as the Yelwa central market in Shendam local government as a good example, this is because the theory posits that conflict is usually exacerbated for material benefits and gains. This clearly shows that the actors who instigated the violent conflict of 2003 and 2004 did so to remain in power and control the central market of Yelwa, which is under study.

1.3 Clarification of Conceptual

To achieve the objectives of this research, concepts such as conflict, crisis, and development need to be properly reviewed and clarified.

Conflict

The word Conflict derived its root from a Latin word “*Conflictus*” which means to strife, clash, or collision. Understanding the ideal meaning of conflict depends on the nature and dynamics of disagreement.²² In general, conflict is perceived as a state of disagreement, social contraction, or a form of opposition between two opposing or incompatible parties.

The term ‘conflict’ is used to describe “a situation in which two or more actors pursue incompatible, yet from their individual perspective entirely just goals.” Conflict sometimes results from the struggle for power and material gain by leaders and followers alike.²³

Conflict is a multi-faceted, universal but complex phenomenon with diverse meanings and structures. According to Dennen, conflict is simply a state of disagreement or opposition between ideas, opinions, and interests.²⁴ Mayer defined conflict as an emotional reaction or tension resulting from incompatible interests, goals, or values that signals disagreement of some kind²⁵. The emotion felt in such a condition might be fear, sadness, bitterness, anger, or hopelessness. Conflict may be described as an open clash between two opposing groups or individuals. This may involve war, battle, or quarrels between individuals or groups. However,

¹⁹Collier, P. (2003). *The economic causes of civil and their Implication*. (Washington DC: World Bank 2003)

²⁰F.S. Ademola, *Theories of social conflicts*, in S.G. Best (Ed.), “*Introduction to Peace and Conflict Studies in West Africa*”: A Reader, Ibadan: Spectrum Books Ltd.2006

²¹Blago Jevic, “Causes of Conflict: A Conceptual Framework,” *Journal of Global Change and Governance*, 3, (2003): 47

²²Asalm Khan “Understanding Conflict” <https://www.managementstudyguide.com> retrieved 2/11/2024

²³Sunday OkungbowaUhunmnanho and AluforoEpella, “Challenges and Solution to Ethno-Religious Conflict in Nigeria: Case study of Jos Crisis,” *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, pp. 57-76. Vol. 13, no. 5, 2011, Clarion University Pennsylvania, Clarion Pennsylvania, 133.

²⁴Dennen J. M. G V. D. (1990). *Introduction on conflict. The sociology of conflict*. (London: Chapman & Hall ,1990),1-1

²⁵Bernard, M. (2000). *The dynamics of conflict resolution: A Practitioner’s Guide*. San-francisco; Jossey Bass.2000), 23

conflict remains a fundamental aspect of human interaction and commonly involves a state of disagreement or collision of interests, values, actions, or emotions between two or more individuals or groups.

Karl Marx (1818–1883) saw²⁶ society as fragmented into groups that compete for social and economic resources. Domination maintains social order, with power in the hands of those with the greatest political, economic, and social resources. When consensus exists, it is attributable to people being united around common interests, often in opposition to other groups, when it exists.

Human beings have different views, opinions, ideas, and conflicting interests. Conflict can be described as a situation or condition of disharmony in an interactional process.

Banks assert that a situation of conflict is one in which one's activity is actually or forcibly imposed at unacceptable costs, materials, or psychic, upon another.²⁷ For conflict to occur, the Banks put forward three factors. These are the intensity and salience of the issue at stake, the status and legitimacy of the parties the clustering of interests, and the coincidence of cleavages within a community. These factors determine the extent to which a conflict can stretch. However, Imobighe points out that conflict is not limited to any particular interaction level. In other words, it could occur at any level of human interaction, and violent activities are often manifested.²⁸

The struggle by each individual to attain such divergent ends at the detriment of other individuals degenerates into antagonistic and violent struggle and destroys social order in communities. Conflict arise in various contexts, such as personal relationships, organizations, societies, and even on a global scale. conflict occur as a result of incompatible interests, needs, beliefs, ideas, behaviour, economic or political marginalization, systemic inequalities, quest for power, status and land among others. What were the factors contributing to the violent conflict outbreak in Yelwa?

Crisis

A crisis refers to “a situation in which the normal functioning of a system, organization, or society is disrupted and its stability, security, or survival is threatened, requiring immediate attention and action to prevent or mitigate harm.”²⁹

A crisis is a state of feeling. It is an internal experience of confusion and anxiety to the degree that formerly successful coping mechanisms fail and ineffective decisions and behaviors take their place. Consequently, the person in crisis may feel confused, vulnerable, anxious, afraid, angry, guilty, hopeless, and helpless. Perceptions are often altered, and memory may be distorted. A crisis state involves the breakdown of coping behaviors that may have been adequate in the past.

In their work *Introduction to Peace and Conflict Resolution Studies*, Piwuna et al. traced the historical origin of the crisis in Nigeria to the Sokoto Jihad of 1804. They further stated that despite the administrative achievement that the jihad brought, the crisis also disrupted commercial activities, such as the trans-Saharan trade.³⁰ Similarly, the Yelwa crisis has distorted the growth of the central Yelwa market.

1.4 Literature Review

Grace. A. Atoshi in her publication *The Story of the Jukun\ Tiv Crisis. Why and How It Happened*.³¹ The author was of the view that the famous Kwararafa Empire, which was a Jukun kingdom, covered the very land that the

²⁶Karl-Marx and Friedrich Engels. *The Communist Manifesto*.Pp.,34

²⁷Banks, A. S. (2002). Warri crises survey report: Urhobo perspective in T. A. Imobighe, C.U. (2002).

²⁸Mobighe, D. (2001). “Trauches or the Secular State: Religion, Politics and the Outlook of Nigeria’s 3rd Republic. *Journal of Commonwealth and Comparative Politics*, xxxvi (2002).

²⁹Herman, Charles F. “Some issues in the study of international crisis: insight from behavioural research.” In Charles F. Herman, 3-17. New York: free press, 1972,4

³⁰Piwuna G. Morgan and Henry.H Longpoe’s *Introduction to Peace and Conflict Resolution Studies*.(Directorate of General Studies, University of Jos) Revised Edition 2022.Pp., 38

³¹Grace Atoshi. *The story of the Jukun\Tiv Crisis Why and how it happened*. (Wukari:Amune Press) 2012

Tiv now call their Local Government Areas. She further opined that the Tiv claim on Wukari Local Government Area as their land was, according to some records from the Tiv, planned long ago for economic and political reasons. In the view of the author, three methods were employed to achieve this. First, by unlawful settlement in land other than theirs. Second, unlawful adjustment of the boundary by being aggressive. An attempt should be made to check their migration and settlement on the land without following a proper channel. This notwithstanding will also be useful for this study. Atoshi's work lacks objective analysis, and the authors' reliance on Jukun records and perspectives may lead to an incomplete picture of the crisis, neglecting Tiv narratives and experiences. Atoshi's work also lacks a critical examination of historical facts. Without a critical evaluation, his acceptance of the historical claims of the Kwarrarafa Empire may overlook the complexities and contestations surrounding historical narratives.

Namsukkim and Pedro Conceicao in "*The Economic Crisis, Violent Conflict, and Human Development*"³² posit that a number of factors could cause conflict. However, empirical studies have found that poor economic performance is associated with a higher incidence of conflict. Being a poor country is correlated with most forms of violence. They also argue that growth rates are strongly associated with the risk of conflict in developing countries. The growth rate in developing countries. Conflict has severe impacts on poverty. Civil war and genocide in the 1990- 2000 period in Rwanda caused convergence between provinces following the conflict shocks: previously richer provinces in the east and north of the country experienced lower, even negative, economic growth compared to the poorer western and southern provinces. This has, in turn, significantly affected the dynamics of household poverty in Rwanda during the same period. They conclude that conflict has major consequences in all aspects of human development, not only income poverty. The work appears to be present the consequences of conflict on the global economy and the increase in poverty rate in conflict areas. Neglecting the impact of violent conflict on commercial centers and traders. A gap that the current study seeks to fill.

In their work, Best and Rakodi³³ posited that, like most countries, violent conflict is also a part of Nigeria's history. Conflicts over access to resources, including land, cattle, and oil. Competition between the various identity groups, they added, has been part of the fabric of the Nigerian state and, as such, has deep historical roots. This has always taken the form of riots, pitting Muslims against Christians and even Islamic sects against each other.

According to the authors, a good number of the outbreaks of violent conflict with a religious dimension have occurred in urban areas, and the violence is episodic with periods of relative calm in many ways. They observed that whenever another outbreak occurs, the social and economic links between communities are permanently disrupted and fractured. As a result, a high level of displacement of people and property destruction are being experienced. They also stated that a distinction can be made between the violent episode itself and the post-conflict period in which normalcy is restored—a period that allows for reconstruction for those affected and a longer period in which social and economic links may be re-established. They argued that Nigeria today is known for its complex and recursive identities, of which ethnic, religious, regional, and sub-ethnic are the main bases of violent conflicts.

According to the authors, the lack of agreement on the number of ethnic groups in the country, with varying estimates from 200 to 500, best illustrates the long-lasting effect of the concept of ethnicity in Nigeria. They

³²Namsuk Kim and C. Pedro "The Economic Crisis, Violent Conflict, and Human Development" *International Journal of Peace Studies*, 15 No 1(2010) : 11-16

³³Best, S. G., & Rakodi, C. (2011). *Violent conflict and its aftermath in Jos and Kano, Nigeria: What is the role of religion?* Religions and Development Research program, Working Paper 69, RaD publications, 2011

also opined that ethnicity is the most basic and politically prominent identity in the country, with citizens more likely to define themselves in terms of ethnic affinity than any other identity, except in the core Islamic areas of northern Nigeria where religion appears to be more prominent. They further stated that, in addition to contending over economic and political power, many conflicts between larger and smaller ethnic groups revolve around land and resources and occasionally erupt into violence, and religious differences between the groups make it even more intense, which made this literature relevant to the current study. Because this has been the situation in Yelwa Shendam crisis. The authors adopted the quantitative method of research in exploring the causes of violent conflict, where questionnaires are used to collect and analyze data. The gap between this literature and the current study is the methodological gap, in which the current study seeks to explore the plethora of conflict using the historical method.

In his book entitled “Religious Conflicts in Northern Nigeria and Nation Building,” Rotgak I. Gofiwen examined³⁴ the causes of conflicts in Northern Nigeria with special emphasis on the conflicts in Kafanchan in 1987, Kano in 1991, and the Kaduna Sharia Crisis in February 2000. He noted that there are different immediate causes of the conflicts. He argued that colonialism created various political, economic, and socio-cultural structures to suit British interests, and these structures now serve as sources of conflicts in Northern Nigeria. He further noted that "in the administration of Nigeria, the political and economic structure which Islam had created were adopted and extended beyond its original frontier: Therein laid the foundation for the perennial religious conflicts in Northern Nigeria."

He opined that, as a result of this Islamic political and socio economic structure adopted by the colonial masters the non-Muslims in the area have consistently complained of "marginalization deprivation in social amenities and economic opportunities and undue subordination of the minorities of southern Kaduna to the emirate system"

The author also observed that the inability of the government to address the complaints of the non-Muslims with regard to marginalization and victimization in the civil services and the failure to implement the recommendations of the previous judicial commission of inquiry will continue to pose a threat to peaceful coexistence in Northern Nigeria. He advised that something remarkable should be done to perfect different interests.

However, it should be noted that even though this book has done a good job of dealing with the causes of religious conflicts in Northern Nigeria, it has also opened up a critical area for research. .However the gap in this literature is the scope of the subject that the current study seeks to explore and document..

1.5 Causes of the crisis in Yelwa Shendam

Yelwa is a settlement established by a group of Jarawa (one of the clans of the jar people) in 1824 who came from the area now known as Bauchi state. Yelwa town presently falls within the present-day Shendam local government area in plateau state, a local government area that hitherto falls within the area known as lowland. This lowland area of plateau state comprises six local governments politically known as southern plateau, a senatorial district of constituency. The dominant ethnic groups occupying the study area are the Goemai and the Jarawa, both of whom claim to be the indigenes of the Yelwa. Subsequently, after the disintegration of the Sokoto caliphate, the Hausa/Fulani also became part of the people in Yelwa. The Jukuns of Taraba also occupied parts Yelwa.

Yelwa a cosmopolitan area, has a large Hausa/Fulani population, as do inhabitants from other tribes in the Shendam local government area. The conflict occurred on two fronts. While Yelwa has a larger Hausa/Fulani population, Shendam is mostly Christian, with a strong influence in the local government administration. The conflict from 2002 to 2003 was relatively domant, but by 2004, it had turned violent, mainly because the

³⁴Rotgak I, Gofwen, “Religious Conflicts in Northern Nigeria and Nation Building”, (Nigeria: Human Right Monitor)

previous agitation had not materialized.³⁵ Therefore, the causes of this conflict are categorized into remote and immediate or proximate causes. Remote causes refer to underlying factors such as **indigene settler causes, political causes, religious causes, and economic causes, whereas** the immediate or proximate causes are those events or activities that spark the crisis's escalation.

1.6 REMOTE CRISIS CAUSES

Indigene settler/ Political causes

Conflicts between indigenous settlers have been a reoccurring theme in scholarly debates. During the colonial and early post-colonial period, Shendam was dominated by migrants, whereas the indigenes made up less than 2% of the town population. Migrants also dominated the economic life in the city because Hausa were traditionally strong in trade and other commercial activities.³⁶ Tension between the indigenes and settlers has long been centered on violent clashes, with both sides claiming ownership and indigenes of the town.

Yelwa-Shendam, an economic hub in the local government, has been contested by the Goemai, who are predominantly Christian and claim the indigene status, asserting historical ownership of the land. The Jarawa, Hausa, and other predominantly Muslim groups that had settlers in the area over generations were labeled as settlers. The Jarawa, in particular, claimed to be the original founders of Yelwa, a claim fiercely contested by the Goemai. Danfulani identify some common names with which the indigenes often called the settlers.

“Labels such as settler native, non-native, ‘host community, foreigner, native foreigner, stranger element, squatter, non-squatter, immigrant, migrant, indigene, ‘non-indigene [...] among many others are used daily in Nigeria to describe, stigmatize or stereotype the ‘other’ as a category who does not belong”³⁷

These names are often viewed by the Jarawa and Hausa settlements as derogatory and demeaning, thereby exacerbating tensions often tied to competing claims over land, commercial centers, and political appointments. Adamu tailor, a former organizing secretary in the Yelwa central market also affirm that ‘the political leadership of the Yelwa central market (from the chairman down to the PRO) was occupied by the Jarawa Hausa.’ This is due to³⁸ their dominance and active participation in the market. Hence, the Goemai feel marginalized on their land. Even after they were given the position of the Secretary according to Adamu, the Goemai were still not satisfied “They were demanding full control of the Yelwa Central Market because they believed that the market was on their soil.”

The above informant narratives align with the economic theory of conflict, whereby individuals struggle to gain economic power in others to control resources for their own personal benefits. These individuals will not only steer conflict but also invest resources at their disposal to achieve their goals.

Added to issues of “indigeneship” in relation to political leadership, disputes over the process of selection of traditional chiefs and, more recently, political rivalry in the context of local elections, particularly elections for the chairmanship of the ruling People’s Democratic Party (PDP) at the PDP ward congress in Yelwa, in April 2002, when tension increased as voters supported candidates along religious lines.

The Goemai, who include both Christians and Muslims, consider themselves “indigenes” and regard the Jarawa as “settlers.” The Jarawa, who are predominantly Muslim, claim to have been the original founders of Yelwa. Until the 1990, the Jarawa and other predominantly Muslim groups such as the Borghom and the Pyem were granted indigene certificates, but from then on, the traditional leader of Shendam, known as the Long Goemai, began denying them indigene rights. Both communities have produced documents attempting to substantiate their “claims” to Yelwa. For example, a document categorically states the Goemai point of view: “We want to

³⁵Anthony, U. I., & Nkwinkol B. “The Political Economy of Plateau State 1994-2012” *An Interdisciplinary Journal of Human theory and praxis* Vol.7 No.1 ISSN 27140-2485 2024

³⁶Working paper and the Geneva Declaration.A deadly cycle: ethno-religious conflict in the jos, plateau

³⁷ Danfulani, Umar Habila Dadem. 2006. ‘The Jos Peace Conference and the Indigene/Settler Question in Nigerian Politics. Leiden and Jos: African Studies center and University of Jos. <<http://www.ascleiden.nl/Pdf/paper-Danfulani.pdf>>

³⁸Oral interview Alhaji Adamu Adamu 61 year’s old, former Yelwa youth organizing secretary. March 14, 2025

reaffirm here that the soul and heart of Yelwa town belong to the Goemai” No amount of intimidation can make us cede that place to any group, no matter how powerful their backers may be. After all Yelwa cannot be an island, since it is surrounded by other Goemai villages.”³⁹ It states that “whoever wants to return to Yelwa and other settlements within Goemai land is free to do so” but adds that “all returnees to Yelwa town [...] must first of all accept the fact that Yelwa is a Goemai town in Goemai land in Plateau State”⁴⁰ A document outlining the Jarawa point of view declares equally emphatically: The original people who founded Yelwa are the Jarawa from Dass in Bauchi State from 1824 to date.⁴¹ Both sides selectively point to historical records to justify their claim to indigene rights to the town of Yelwa.

In relation to the power theory by Morgenthau Hans, societies struggle to control power, with incompatible interests creating room for conflict. This is clearly evident in the contestation between the Goemai, Jarawa, and the hausa communities in Shendam, the Goemai trying to exist their power as the indigenes of the town.

*Conflicts have significantly disrupted the state's functionality since Nigeria's independence, with the Nigerian Civil War (1967–1971) being a notable example. While the conflict in Plateau State shares similarities with other regional conflicts, it stands out due to its use of indigene status as a criterion for political, economic, and resource allocation. Religious differences have often acted as catalysts, intensifying the violence between indigenes and settlers competing for resources.*⁴²

The indigene settler factors in the 2002 and 2004 yelwa shendam crisis were remote because they established a structural framework of inequality, exclusion, and competition that predated violence. Competing claims to land, discriminatory policies, political power struggles, historical narratives, and socioeconomic disparities created a tinderbox where minor disputes could ignite widespread conflict.

Religious causes

Historically, religion was not a primary cause of conflict in the area. However, in recent years, the situation has become increasingly polarized, and ethnic groups, including the Fulani, the Tarok, and a number of smaller groups from other local government areas, have taken sides largely along religious lines. For example, a Christian from the Angas ethnic group in Yelwa asserted that: “As indigenes of Plateau State, we cannot leave this place to them [the Muslims].” The Goemai are the indigenes of the Shendam local government. The Angas perceive themselves as the indigenes of the Plateau State. The Muslims in Yelwa are now non-indigenes. They come from the northern states ... It's a religious war. They said they were the indigenes of this place and wanted to chase us out. They want to occupy the place.”⁴³

None of the interviewed individuals cited religion as a fundamental cause of the conflict. However, as documented below, when the fighting began, groups and individuals were targeted based on religion rather than ethnicity. Mosques and churches were deliberately attacked. Religion was used as a rallying cry to drag other groups into the conflict, and both sides used explicitly religious language to defend their position or tarnish their opponents. A local government official in Shendam explained the transformation of the conflict as follows: “There has always been an indigene/settler issue. Indigene tribes and settlers both insist that they own the land. “Religion is a cover [...] but anything that happens now is turned into a religious issue.”⁴⁴

The run-up to the violence in Yelwa is a political crisis centered on a dispute over the town's political power. This came to a head in May 2002, when new districts were created in Plateau State's southern senatorial zone. Yelwa is a Muslim majority in population, but rather than being made a separate district, it was placed within

³⁹Fidelis Longban: “Who are the Goemai...67

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⁴¹Human Right Watch No. 1.Vol2

⁴²Umoh A. Imeh & Nwinkol Barinaadaa. The Political Economy of Conflict in Plateau State 1994-2012; *An Interdisciplinary Journal of Human Theory and Praxis*, 7 (1), ISSN (online) 2714-2485

⁴³Oral interview with Rotgak Gomiyar yam seller 60yrs 18 April 2025

⁴⁴Rotgak Gomiyar18April2025

Nshar District under the authority of Shendam, a Goemai (mainly Catholic) town.⁴⁵ This gave political recognition to Goemai claims to indigeneity in the area, rather than to Muslims in Yelwa, and to the control of the Long Goemai (the Goemai paramount ruler) over Yelwa. Although the chief in Yelwa would likely be a Muslim, he would be appointed by the Long Goemai rather than selected from among his constituency and formally installed by the Long Goemai. Muslims in Yelwa wanted their own district as a step toward creating a new local government area. This would provide financial opportunities for the local elite and raise the profile of Yelwa in Plateau politics.⁴⁶ The dispute over the chieftaincy was exacerbated in the first week of June 2002 by a disagreement at the ward congress of the People's Democratic Party (PDP) (the ruling party in Nigeria) over who should become chairman in Yelwa-Nshar ward. Muslims wanted the existing chairman to continue in office, whereas Christians wanted the position to be rotated. A Christian candidate was put forward and the position was contested in an open ballot, whereby voters for each candidate gathered into separate lines to be counted. A fight broke out between the lines, which had separated according to religion due to bloc voting. Some people were injured, but no one was reported to have been killed. The election was canceled, but as Muslims formed a majority, their candidate was appointed as the PDP ward chairman. Both sides agree that the congress deeply divided Yelwa along religious lines.⁴⁷

The struggle for political position in Yelwa under the PDP further explicitly explains and makes evident the manifestation of the power theory adopted for this study.

At the time, the chairman of the vigilante group in Yelwa was a Christian from Delta State.. Muslim say this was not an issue until the crisis, as the vigilante group in the town was centralized and had Muslim and Christian members working together. However, as political tensions mounted, Christians in Yelwa responded by trying to prevent their women from having extramarital relations with Muslim men. This divided the vigilantes, as only Christian vigilantes enforced the ban. It constituted a form of "within-group" vigilance exercised by what appears to have been a loose collective of Christian youths in Yelwa.⁴⁸ They harassed and stopped Christian girls whom they suspected of having sexual relations with Muslims, but Muslims claim they also harassed and even beat up some of the Muslim boys. The more general reaction of the Christian women in Yelwa to this sanction is Unclear. In defense of their actions, some Christians pointed out that Muslim youths seek relationships with Christian women, but Christian men cannot form relationships with Muslim women..

1.7 IMMEDIATE CRISIS CAUSE AND OUTBREAK

Interviewees described three major outbreaks of violence in Yelwa town: the first on June 26, 2002, the second on February 24, 2004, and the third on May 2-3, 2004. All three incidents involved deliberate attacks. In all three cases, the victims included both Christians and Muslims. However, most victims in February 24, 2004 attack were Christians, while most victims in the May 2004 attack were Muslims.⁴⁹

In the early hours of June 26, 2002, the night-watchman (maigadi) of the Izala mosque in Anguwan Galadima, a predominantly Christian neighborhood of Yelwa, was stabbed (wounded but not killed). A security meeting involving politicians, traditional and religious leaders, and security and police officers was held at the local government offices in Shendam that morning to address the growing crisis, but violence broke out that night. Christians claim that the sanction they placed on their women led to a fight on the street in the town's Anguwan Pandam area on the night of June 26 in which a Christian was killed.⁵⁰ Christians frequently cited this as the trigger for the 2002 violence in Yelwa and the start of the wider crisis. Muslims say the crisis started when masquerades were heard coming toward town from the shrine at Anguwan Pandam the same night.

⁴⁵Human Right Watch

⁴⁶bid

⁴⁷Oral interview at Galadima Yelwa Palace 76 years ago on April 10, 2025

⁴⁸bid

⁴⁹Human Rights Watch, Revenge in the Name of Religion: The Cycle of Violence in Plateau and Kano States, Vol. 17No.82005

⁵⁰Oral interview with David Lala Kwapshar, a 56-year-old former Goemai youth leader, yelwa, April 18, 2025

Eyewitnesses said a large crowd was following the masquerade, and many of them were carrying machetes and other weapons. Several witnesses claimed that the armed people taunted and threatened Muslims and challenged them to come out. They noticed a mosque on fire in the Angwan Pandam area and then saw another building burning in a different area. Muslims reportedly came out of their homes, confronted the people in the masquerade, and the violence began. A witness described it as “effective mobilization in both camps.” Muslims came out in droves. Christians did too.” The fighting lasted until around 4 a.m. the following morning, when soldiers were sent to Yelwa to restore peace.

Muslims claim that the masquerades were part of an armed group, precipitating the crisis when a Muslim youth was killed and the mosque burned in Anguwan Pandam. All of this may have happened, but the sequence of events remains unclear.⁵¹ Oral interviews and written memoranda to the government by Muslim and Christian leaders in Yelwa emphasize different. An interview with one of the residents of Yelwa named Adamu Adamu stated that the reprisal attack claimed the lives of Umar, his neighbor’s son, and his own son. In his work, Higazi captured that there are varying estimates of the number of casualties in Yelwa in 2002, ranging from 50 to over 200 killed Muslims and Christians.⁵²

Some Yelwa residents described another possible catalyst for the fighting. They mentioned that as tensions between Christians and Muslims had been rising, Christian community leaders issued a directive that their young women should not befriend young Muslim men and that anyone caught doing so would be punished. Some interviewees alleged that this directive was one of the factors that sparked the violence but did not provide clear evidence of a direct link between the two.

Conclusion

Violent conflict is a serious phenomenon that has been bedeviling not only Yelwa but the entire Shendam local government area, with concomitant effects of loss of lives and property. Yelwa town, which is the economic hub of Shendam local government and also houses the most active market (Yelwa central market), has been severely distorted and destroyed as a result of the violent conflict that engulfed the town. Moreover, as a result of the crisis, some sectors of the market broke out and became satellite markets; examples of such include the Nshar yam market, which broke out from the central market, largely formed by Christian. The cattle market during the crisis was moved to a called Garkawa in the Mikang local government, which underscored the massive loss of revenue to the Shendam local government.

The study concludes by illustrating the grave consequences of the Nigerian government’s persistent neglect of communal tensions and of its failure to take action to prevent longstanding grievances from turning into violence. Both the federal and state governments failed to respond to the three years of intermittent fighting in Yelwa, until the situation became uncontrollable. Had the government acted much earlier, notably by bringing those responsible for the violence to justice, hundreds of lives might have been saved during the massacres in Yelwa in Crisis. When government forces finally intervened, their intervention came far too late,

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⁵¹Adam Higazi’s Social Mobilization and Collective Violence: Vigilantes and Militias in the Plateau State’s Lowlands Africa 78 (1) (2008)

⁵²Adam Higazi, “Social Mobilization and Collective Violence,” p. 117

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